

Dihydroresorcinols. Part II. The Condensation of Aldehydes with *cyclo*Pentane-*spiro*-*cyclo*hexane-3:5-dione and Dimethyldihydroresorcinol.

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It was the original intention of the author to prepare tetrahydrobenzopyranol dyes from various dihydroresorcinols of the general formula (I) where R, R₁ = H, alkyl, aryl, *cyclopentane* and *cyclohexane* radicals, with a view to studying their absorption spectra, in order to determine the effect exerted by alkyl and *gem*-dialkyl groups on the colour of these substances. Owing to difficulties met with in their utmost purification which was necessary for this type of work, the project had to be abandoned. In the meanwhile, a paper on the condensation of dimethyldihydroresorcinol with aromatic aldehydes was published by Chakravarti, Chattopadhyaya and Ghosh (*J. Ind. Inst. Sci.*, 1931, **14A** 141). This rendered much of the present author's work on dimethyldihydroresorcinol superfluous but the results obtained so far with *cyclopentanespirocyclohexane*-3:5-dione (II) are interesting enough for publication.

The action of benzaldehyde on dimethyldihydroresorcinol (I, R = R₁ = Me) and phenyldihydroresorcinol (I, R = H; R₁ = Ph) had already been studied by Vorländer (*Annalen*, 1899, **309**, 379) who showed that the primary products formed were benzalbisdihydroresorcinols (III, X = H) which were easily convertible by dehydration into the corresponding diketooctahydroxanthenes (IV, X = H).

(IV)

The author observed that compound (III) was formed much more readily in presence of piperidine as a catalyst, whilst compound (IV) was exclusively formed with hydrogen chloride as a condensing agent. The behaviour of *cyclopentanespiro-cyclohexane-3:5-dione* was exactly similar, and benzaldehyde as well as salicylaldehyde reacted with the dione (II), at the ordinary temperature in presence of piperidine as a condensing agent, giving benzal-bis-*cyclopentanespiro-*

cyclohexane-3:5-dione (III, X=H and $C \begin{matrix} \nearrow R \\ \searrow R_1 \end{matrix} = C < C_4H_8$) and salical-

bis-*cyclopentanespiro-cyclohexane-3:5-dione* (III, X=OH and $C \begin{matrix} \nearrow R \\ \searrow R_1 \end{matrix} = C < C_4H_8$).

The dehydration of the benzal derivative by acetic anhydride, glacial acetic acid or dry hydrogen chloride gave 2-*spiro-cyclopentane-4:5-diketo-7-spiro-cyclopentane-9-phenyloctahydroxan-*

thene (IV, X=H and $C \begin{matrix} \nearrow R \\ \searrow R_1 \end{matrix} = C < C_4H_8$). Under the same condi-

tions, the salical derivative could give rise either to 2-*spiro-cyclopentane-4:5-diketo-7-spiro-cyclopentane-9-o-hydroxyphenyloctahydroxan-*

xanthene (IV, X=OH and $C \begin{matrix} \nearrow R \\ \searrow R_1 \end{matrix} = C < C_4H_8$) or to the pyran deriva-

tive (V). But the product formed was the octahydroxanthene derivative, as acetyl salicylaldehyde condensed with the (II), giving acetyl-salicalbis-*cyclopentanespiro-cyclohexane-3:5-dione* (III, X=O·COCH₃

and $C \begin{matrix} \nearrow R \\ \searrow R_1 \end{matrix} = C < C_4H_8$) which could be dehydrated to the octa-

hydroxanthene derivative, identical with the one formed by the acetylation of 2-*spiro-cyclopentane-4:5-diketo-7-spiro-cyclopentane-9-o-hydroxyphenyloctahydroxanthene*.

(V)

(VI)

When salicylaldehyde was condensed with the dione (II) in presence of dry hydrogen chloride, a scarlet compound was formed and this was found to be 2-*spiro-cyclopentane-4-ketotetrahydrobenzopyranol-anhydrochloride* (VI). Other dihydroresorcinols behaved similarly and this reaction was studied with dimethyldihydroresorcinol, phenyldihydroresorcinol and *cyclohexanespiro-cyclohexane-3:5-dione*. Thus these dihydroresorcinols behaved like α -hydrindone and diketohydrindene from which pyranol dyes have already been prepared (Perkin, Robinson and Turner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 23, 1085; Sastry and Ghosh, *ibid.*, 1915, 107, 1442).

The formation of the anhydrochloride (VI) must have involved the intermediate formation of *salicylidene-cyclopentane-spiro-cyclohexane-3:5-dione* but attempts to prepare it from the aldehyde and the dione (II) by condensing them with or without the alkaline as well as acid condensing agents failed. The hydrolysis of the anhydrochloride (VI) with strong caustic potash was also tried, but the resulting product was the anhydro base (VI, OH in place of Cl) which resisted the action of the alkali. Similarly the dimethyl analogue of the anhydro base was unaffected by the action of caustic alkali. The stability of these anhydro bases could only be accounted for by the presence of a *cyclopentane* nucleus and a *gem*-dimethyl group. That this sort of stabilising effect is exerted by the

gem-dimethyl group has its parallel in the observation of Vorländer (*Annalen*, 1896, 294, 275) who failed to hydrolyse dimethyldihydroresorcinol to $\beta\beta$ -dimethyl- γ -acetobutyric acid while dihydroresorcinol readily underwent hydrolysis to γ -acetobutyric acid.

By condensing salicylaldehyde with dimethyldihydroresorcinol in presence of caustic potash, Chakravarti, Chattopadhyaya and Ghosh (*loc. cit.*) obtained a product melting at 206°, and having the empirical formula $C_{23}H_{26}O_4$. These authors formulated it as *o*-hydroxybenzaldimethyldihydroresorcinol anhydride [V, $C < C_4H_8 = C(CH_3)_2$]. In assigning the pyran structure, the arguments advanced were neither cogent nor conclusive. The present author is of opinion that the above compound can best be formulated as the xanthene derivative, and should be called 2:2:7:7-tetramethyl-4:5-diketo-9-*o*-hydroxyphenyloctahydroxanthene (IV, X=OH, R=R₁=CH₃). This constitution is supported by the fact that the acetyl derivative of this compound is identical with the dehydration product of acetylsalicylbisdimethyldihydroresorcinol (III, X=O·CO·CH₃; R=R₁=CH₃) which is formed by the condensation of acetylsalicylaldehyde with dimethyldihydroresorcinol in presence of piperidine at ordinary temperature; also its methylated product is identical with the dehydrated product of *o*-methoxybenzalbisdimehyldihydroresorcinol (III, X=OCH₃; R=R₁=CH₃) which is obtained by the action of *o*-methoxybenzaldehyde on dimethyldihydroresorcinol.

EXPERIMENTAL.

*cyclo*Pentanespiro-*cyclo*hexane-3:5-dione was prepared by the method of Norris and Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1205). When its alcoholic solution was treated with an excess of 40% formaldehyde solution at ordinary temperature methylenebis*cyclo*-pentanespiro*cyclo*hexane-3:5-dione was immediately precipitated, m. p. 165°.

2-spiro-*cyclo*Pentane-4:5-diketo-7-spiro-*cyclo*pentane-octahydroxanthene.—The above methylene derivative (1 g.) was heated with acetic anhydride (5 c. c.) on a free flame for 3 hours and the excess of the anhydride decomposed by adding water. The precipitated solid crystallised from alcohol as tiny, white needles, m. p. 180-81°.

(Found: C, 77.1; H, 8.1. $C_{21}H_{26}O_3$ requires C, 77.3; H, 8.0 per cent).

Benzal-bis-cyclopentanespiro-cyclohexane-3:5-dione [III, X = H, $C \begin{matrix} \swarrow R \\ \searrow R_1 \end{matrix} = C < C_4H_8$].—A mixture of benzaldehyde (2 g.), *cyclopentane-spiro-cyclohexane-3:5-dione* (3.5 g.), dry benzene (25 c. c.) and piperidine (4 drops) was kept at the ordinary temperature for 12 hours. The residue left after the removal of benzene under suction crystallised from dilute alcohol as white plates or needles, m. p. 167°. Its alcoholic solution gives a reddish-brown colouration with ferric chloride solution. (Found: C, 77.0; H, 7.8. $C_{27}H_{32}O_4$ requires C, 77.1; H, 7.6 per cent).

2-spiro-cyclopentane-4:5-diketo-7-spiro-cyclopentane-9-phenylocta-hydroxanthene (IV, X = H, $C (R R_1) = C < C_4H_8$).—When the above compound (1 g.) was heated with acetic anhydride (5 c. c.) on a free flame for 15-20 minutes and the excess of the anhydride decomposed with water, a solid was precipitated. This crystallised from alcohol as compact cubes, m. p. 185-86°. Its alcoholic solution does not give colouration with ferric chloride solution. (Found: C, 80.4; H, 7.6. $C_{27}H_{30}O_3$ requires C, 80.6; H, 7.5 per cent).

Salical-bis-cyclopentanespiro-cyclohexane-3:5-dione [III, X = OH, $C (R R_1) = C < C_4H_8$].—A mixture of salicylaldehyde (2 g.), *cyclopentanespiro-cyclohexane-3:5 dione* (3.4 g.), dry benzene (20 c. c.) and piperidine (4 drops) was kept at the room temperature for 12 hours. The solid that separated out crystallised from alcohol as white plates, m. p. 208-09°. It is readily soluble in dilute caustic alkali and its alcoholic solution gives reddish violet colouration with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 74.2; H, 7.4. $C_{27}H_{32}O_5$ requires C, 74.3; H, 7.3 per cent).

2-spiro-cyclopentane-4:5-diketo-7-spiro-cyclopentane-9-o-hydroxy phenyloctahydroxanthene (IV, X = OH, $C (R R_1) = C < C_4H_8$).—The above compound (1 g.) was boiled with glacial acetic acid (15 c. c.) for 4 hours. On dilution, white needles melting to a red liquid at 191° were obtained. It is soluble in alkali and its alcoholic solution gives a violet colouration with ferric chloride. The same

substance could also be prepared by saturating the absolute alcoholic solution of the foregoing salical derivative with dry hydrogen chloride at 0° and keeping for 12 hours. (Found: C, 77.3; H, 7.2. $C_{27}H_{30}O_4$ requires C, 77.5; H, 7.2 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative was prepared by heating either the salical derivative or the xanthene derivative with acetic anhydride for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour on a sand-bath. The solid left after decomposing the excess of the anhydride crystallised from dilute alcohol as prismatic needles, m. p. $181-82^\circ$. (Found: C, 75.6; H, 7.1. $C_{29}H_{32}O_5$ requires C, 75.6; H, 7.0 per cent).

The *benzoyl* derivative was prepared by treating the pyridine solution of the xanthene derivative with benzoyl chloride. On dilution with water an oil, which slowly solidified, was obtained. It crystallised from alcohol in plates, m. p. 137° . (Found: C, 78.1; H, 6.6. $C_{34}H_{34}O_5$ requires C, 78.2; H, 6.5 per cent).

Acetylsalicalbiscyclopentanespiro-cyclohexane-3:5-dione [III, X = O·COCH₃, C (R R₁) = C <C₄H₈].—This was prepared, like the benzal analogue, by using acetylsalicylaldehyde and crystallised from dilute alcohol in white needles, m. p. 206° . Its mixed m. p. with salical-bis-cyclopentanespiro-cyclohexane-3:5-dione was $180-84^\circ$, and the alcoholic solution gives a reddish brown colouration with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 72.5; H, 7.2. $C_{29}H_{34}O_6$ requires C, 72.8; H, 7.1 per cent).

When this substance was boiled with acetic anhydride for 15 minutes or glacial acetic acid for 4 hours, the resulting product was identified as the acetyl derivative of the diketooctahydroxanthene derivative by the m. p. and mixed m. p.

2-spiro-cyclopentane-4-diketotetrahydrobenzopyranol anhydrochloride. (VI).—A solution of *cyclopentane-spiro-cyclohexane-3:5-dione* (1 g.) and salicylaldehyde (7 g.) in absolute methyl alcohol (10 c. c.) was saturated with a rapid current of dry hydrogen chloride at 0° . The mixture became dark red and viscous and on keeping overnight scarlet crystals were deposited. These were filtered off, and washed on the filter paper with methyl alcohol saturated with dry hydrogen chloride. It is sparingly soluble in most of the organic solvents and charred without melting at 300° . The sample for analysis was dried in a vacuum over caustic potash. (Found: C, 70.6; H, 6.0; Cl, 11.5. $C_{17}H_{17}O_2Cl$ requires C, 70.7; H, 5.9; Cl, 12.3 per cent).

The *anhydro base* was prepared by adding sodium acetate solution to the warm solution of the anhydro-chloride in a large excess of ethyl alcohol. The pink powder that was precipitated was filtered off and washed alternately with water, alcohol and ether. It is sparingly soluble in the usual organic solvents, and does not melt below 300°. It was recovered unchanged after heating with a concentrated solution of alcoholic caustic potash, and the anhydro-chloride was formed on adding it to methyl alcohol saturated with dry hydrogen chloride. (Found: C, 75.4; H, 6.8. $C_{17}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 75.6; H, 6.7 per cent).

Dimethyldihydroresorcinol was prepared by the method of Vorländer (*Annalen*, 1897, 294, 253). The hydrolysis of the dione ester was carried out by alcoholic potash, as this required only 3 to 4 hours, yield 80%.

Benzalbisdimethyldihydroresorcinol was prepared from benzaldehyde and dimethyldihydroresorcinol, like the cyclopentane analogue. It crystallises from alcohol as white plates, m. p. 196-97° and gives violet colouration with ferric chloride. The m. p. given by Vorländer (*loc. cit.*) is 193°, while that given by Chakravarti, Chattopadhyaya and Ghosh (*loc. cit.*) is 175-76°. (Found: C, 74.9; H, 7.9. Calc: C, 75.0; H, 7.6 per cent).

2:2:7:7-Tetramethyl-4:5-diketo-9-phenyloctahydrozanthene was prepared from the above substance by dehydrating it with glacial acetic acid, acetic anhydride or dry hydrogen chloride and crystallised from alcohol as white needles, m.p. 202°. The m.p. given by Chakravarti, Chattopadhyaya and Ghosh (*loc. cit.*) is 193°. (Found: C, 78.9; H, 7.5. Calc: C, 78.8; H, 7.4 per cent).

The *phenylhydrazone* prepared by heating the substance with an equivalent amount of phenylhydrazine in glacial acetic acid solution for 1 hour on a water-bath crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles, m.p. 266-67° (decomp.). (Found: C, 78.9; H, 7.4. $C_{29}H_{32}O_2N_2$ requires C, 79.1; H, 7.3 per cent).

Salicalbisdimethyldihydroresorcinol was prepared from salicylaldehyde and dimethyldihydroresorcinol like its benzal analogue and crystallised from dilute alcohol in white plates, m.p. 184°. (Found: C, 71.7; H, 7.5. $C_{23}H_{28}O_5$ requires C, 71.9; H, 7.3 per cent).

When this was heated with glacial acetic acid for 4 hours, *2:2:7:7-tetramethyl-4:5-diketo-9-o-hydroxyphenyl-octahydrozanthene* (IV, X=OH, R=R₁=CH₃), which crystallised from alcohol in white

rhombohedra, m.p. 209-10° was formed. The same substance is also formed by condensing salicylaldehyde with dimethyldihydroresorcinol in presence of caustic potash. (cf. Chakravarti, Chattopadhyaya and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*). (Found: C, 75.3; H, 7.3. Calc: C, 75.4; H, 7.1 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared by heating the above compound with acetic anhydride, crystallised from dilute alcohol in prismatic needles, m.p. 190-91°. (Found: C, 73.3; H, 6.9. Calc: C, 73.5; H, 6.8 per cent).

The *benzoyl* derivative crystallised from dilute alcohol in clusters of white, tiny needles, m.p. 154-55°. (Found: C, 76.7; H, 6.6. Calc: C, 76.6; H, 6.4 per cent).

The *phenylhydrazone* crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 235°. (Found: C, 76.1; H, 7.3. $C_{29}H_{32}O_2N_2$ requires C, 76.3; H, 7.0 per cent).

The *methyl ether* (IV, $X = OCH_3$; $R = R_1 = CH_3$) prepared by heating the substance (0.5 g.) with methyl iodide (2. c.c.) at 100° for 12 hours, crystallised from dilute alcohol in white needles, m.p. 180°. (Found: C, 75.6; H, 7.5. $C_{24}H_{28}O_4$ requires C, 75.8; H, 7.4 per cent).

Acetylsalicyldimethyldihydroresorcinol (III, $X = O \cdot COCH_3$; $R = R_1 = CH_3$).—This was prepared, like the *cyclopentane* analogue, from acetylsalicylaldehyde and dimethyldihydroresorcinol and crystallised from dilute alcohol in white needles, m.p. 200-01°. Its alcoholic solution gives colouration with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 71.1; H, 6.9. $C_{26}H_{30}O_6$ requires C, 71.2; H, 6.8 per cent).

When this substance was dehydrated either by heating with acetic anhydride (30 min.) or glacial acetic acid (4 hours) or saturating its absolute alcoholic solution with hydrogen chloride, the resulting product was identified as the acetyl derivative of 2:2:7:7-tetramethyl-4:5-diketo-9-o-hydroxyphenyl-octahydroxanthene by m.p. and mixed m.p.

o-Methoxybenzalbisdimethyldihydroresorcinol (III, $X = OCH_3$, $R = R_1 = CH_3$).—This was prepared like the preceding compound by using *o*-methoxybenzaldehyde and crystallised from dilute alcohol in white tiny needles, m.p. 184°. Its m.p. was depressed to 156° by admixture with a specimen of salicylbisdimethyldihydroresorcinol which had also the same melting point. Its alcoholic solution gives violet-blue colouration with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 72.3; H, 7.7. $C_{24}H_{30}O_5$ requires C, 72.4; H, 7.5 per cent). When

it was dehydrated by the usual methods, the resulting product was identified as the methyl ether of 2:2:7:7-tetramethyl-4:5-diketo-9-o. hydroxyphenyloctahydroxanthene by m.p. and mixed m. p.

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